

**EFFECT OF ORGANIZATIONAL JUSTICE ON EMPLOYEE
COMMITMENT PERCEIVED ORGANIZATIONAL SUPPORT AS A MEDIATING
VARIABLE IN THE CASE OF GONDAR CITY ADMINISTRATION REVENUE
OFFICE**

ZERIHUN KINDE ALEMU

Email: zeracoc4@gmail.com, Ethiopian Civil Service University, Ethiopia, Addis Ababa.

ABSTRACT

The main aim of this study was to examine the effect of Organizational justice on employee commitment and examine perceived organizational support as a mediating variable in Gondar city administration revenue office. To execute the research objective, the study uses primary data collection method through a structured questionnaire, developed based on Close-ended 5-point Likert scale and distributed by using simple random sampling technique to 202 respondents and all are collected. Secondary data collected from magazine, websites and others relevant sources. Collected data was analyzed using descriptive (frequency and percentages) and inferential statistical tools including linear regression, Pearson Correlation, multiple regression. To understand the effect of distributive justice, procedural justice, interactional justice on employee commitment Statistical Package for Social Science (SPSS) version 25 software was utilized as the analytical technique of choice. From the result of the analysis, it is concluded that distributive justice, procedural justice and interactional justice is positive and significantly effect with employee commitment and there is positively and significant relationship perceived organizational support and employee commitment. In addition to this perceived organizational support have a mediating role on the relationship between organizational justice and employee commitment. To keep the benefit of having committed employee and retaining capable and skilled employee the importance of organizational justice in the workplace is vital.

Keyword: Employee Commitment, Perceived Organizational Support, organizational justice, distributive justice, procedural justice, interactional justice.

INTRODUCTION

1.1 BACK GROUND OF THE STUDY

In recent time, organizational justice, or equity in the workplace, has emerged as an important concept to learn about workplace attitudes and behavior (Cropanzano & Rupp, 2003; Ambrose, Hess & Ganesan, 2007). Job satisfaction, salary satisfaction, and organizational commitment have all been shown to be good predictors of employees' perceptions of justice (Cohen-Charash & Spector, 2001; Colquitt, Conlon, Wesson, Porter & Ng, 2001). "organizational justice is central and expressed as the perception of fairness in an organization by its workforce" (Greenberg, 1990). It is thought that committed employees will positively impacted on the success of businesses (Cropanzano & Stein, 2009). However, their organizational commitment is endangered if they felt unfairly treated (Hassan, 2002). Accordingly, to ease the threat, organizational justice is an important tool. Employees are very curious and react on environment that are perceived to be unfair (Skarlicki & Folger, 1997). According to Rawls (1971) there are three dimensions of organization justice. These are procedural justice, distributive justice, and interpersonal justice.

The first type of organizational Justice is Distributive Justice where the perception of an employee deals with the fairness in the outcome irrespective of the procedure followed to achieve it (Greenberg, 1990). The issue of outcome fairness is generally outlined as reward allocation wherever the parameter of individuals labor and its relevancy reward allocation is taken in to thought (Greenberg, 1990).

The second type of justice is Procedural Justice is to provide fair procedural practice and the perceptions of employees will accept the outcome irrespective of its relevancy to their own benefit (Greenberg, 1990). For example, once comparison two people the variable of quality still as amount can acquire the image wherever amount is going to be the quantity of labor performed whereas the variable of quality would be the efficiency with which the work was performed, when considering this example in a manufacturing industry it would be not only the number of parts produced but also the number of errors committed while making these parts (Greenberg, 1990).

The third type of Organizational Justice is Interactional Justice which is the newest found justice which deals with the factors of Informational Justice and Interpersonal (Sam Fricchione, 2006). Interpersonal Justice deals with dignity and respect towards employee by his subordinates and manager (Sam Fricchione, 2006). Informational justice will deal with the factors of communication between the employees and the manager(Sam Fricchione, 2006).

perceived organizational support refers to employee's perception regarding about the organizational values, their involvement and cares about their well-being (Eisenberger & Rhoades, 2002). Perceived organizational support includes the formation of general beliefs of staff, in connection with how much an organization is interested in the welfare of employees and values for their contribution (Khulida,Fairuzah& Ari, 2012). In fact, perceived organizational support is organization's commitment to its employees (Leenu&Lakhwinder, 2012)

The sustainable success of an organization is essentially dependent on employee's organizational commitment and hence the concept has fascinated many researchers in helping organizations to be productive and achieving their long-term missions and visions (Meyer & Allen, 1991). Committed employees are thought to have higher job satisfaction, intensify performance and reduced intention to leave their organization (Ali et al., 2010). Employee's organizational commitment is also thought to be one of the primary determinants of workers' performance and business success. In order to obtain the greatest out of their employees and sustain their success, organizations are expected to know what factors are affecting the organizational commitment of their work force (Ali et al., 2010). Employee's organizational commitment is an effective response to the whole organization and the degree of attachment or devotion employees feel towards their organization (Wei & Tai, 2010). Employees with poor organizational commitment do not exercise their full potential into the work and realizing mission of their employers (Ali et al., 2010). Even if organization may design and institute fair compensation policies and human resource practices to stimulate and retain employees, most of times, they would fail to recognize why some employees are not attachment to the organization (Allen & Mayer, 1991). It can be costly if workers are not committed in their jobs, and if they lack the enthusiasm to work out their full capacities (Ongori, 2007).

Therefore, the study would examine Organizational Justice and its effects on employee commitment and Perceived Organizational Support as mediating variable in Gondar City administration revenue office. The result of the research would expect to support organization's management in giving attention to how it may enhance the organizational commitment of its employees, that were not addressed before.

1.2 STATEMENT OF THE PROBLEM

Organizational justice plays an important role in employees' organizational commitment towards their organizational overall productivity also If the process for achieving an outcome is perceived to be fair, in that case even an unfair outcome is acceptable, hence It is considered that a perception of organizational justice has an effect on employee's satisfaction of regarding their jobs and their commitment towards organizations (Asim et al.,2016)

In organizational settings, justice is not always managed through fair allocation of employment resources, provision of clear and adequate descriptions for decisions made and employees are not always treated with dignity and respect during the implementation of policies and procedures (Gurbuz & Mert, 2009)

great number of employees have lost their loyalty and absence of organizational commitment because of several forms of organizational injustice (Skarlicki&Folger, 1997). enhancing organizational commitment among the organizational members is an important factor that will ultimately result in their higher workforce organizational commitment, reducing leavers and they will accomplish better (Nawab, 2011). Committed workforce give a visible advantage and hardly few organizations in this aspirant world could realize their target without (Allen & Mayer, 1990).

In a study applied in Kenya and other developing countries, the researchers found that regardless of the affiliation, mission, size and extent of operations, issues of low morale and low motivation of workers were prevalent in governmental organizations. All are causes and outcomes of commitment. it indicates the absence of organizational justice and low employee commitment. (Gichira, 2016)

Moreover, there is no study has also been conducted in Ethiopian in the area of organizational justice and its effect on employee's commitment by considering perceived organizational support as a mediating factor. Besides, in Ethiopian context, there are insufficient academic literatures in the area of organizational justice to examine its relationship with employee's organizational commitment and organizational support as a mediating factor.

Therefore, the study would attempt to fill the gap by investigating the relationship between the three dimensions of organizational justice (i.e., distributive justice, procedural justice and interactional justice) and employee's commitment and the mediating role of organizational support on the relationships between the three dimensions of organizational justice and employee's commitment intention in the context of Gondar city administration revenue office and Fill the gap by creating clear understanding on the result between three dimension of organizational justice, employee's commitment and organizational support.

1.3 OBJECTIVE OF THE STUDY

1.3.1 GENERAL OBJECTIVE

The general objective of the study is to examine the effect of organizational justice on employee's commitment and examine the effect of organizational support as a mediating role.

1.3.2 SPECIFIC OBJECTIVE

The study has the following specific objectives: -

1. To examine the effect of three dimensions of organizational justice (i.e., distributive justice, procedural justice and interactional justice) on employee's commitment.
2. To examine the effect of three dimensions of organizational justice (i.e., distributive justice, procedural justice and interactional justice) on organizational support.
3. To identify the effect of organizational support on employee's commitment.
4. To investigate the mediating role of organizational support in the relationship between organizational justice (i.e., distributive justice, procedural justice and interactional justice) and employee's commitment.

2.LITERATURE REVIEW

2.1 ORGANIZATIONAL JUSTICE AND EMPLOYEE'S COMMITMENT

Many researchers have empirically studied two concepts of organizational justice and organizational commitment, and the studies have largely confirmed a positive relationship between them (Moon et al., 2014;Imran et al., 2015; Kofi et al., 2016). More specifically, several studies have focused on examining the relationship between organizational justice and affective commitment. Conclusions from those studies reveal that when an organization's employees perceive that high levels of organizational justice, they manifest higher levels of affective organizational commitment (Rego& Cunha, 2008; Colquitt et al., 2013; Moon et al., 2014; Ohana& Meyer, 2016).

Folger&Konovsky (1989) conclude that perceived distributive justice does not affect trust and commitment because of the quid pro quo matters concerning fairness in the exchange of labor for compensation. The employees, Distributive justice does not have any impact on the perception of the supervisor because fair pay for work is what most organizations are expected to provide whereas procedural justice increases organizational commitment and trust in supervisors or in those making allocating decisions.

The study will identify the influence of organizational justice on employees' commitment in manufacturing firms in Oyo state, Nigeria: implications for industrial social works by using organizational justice theory with the study investigated the influence of organizational justice on organizational commitment in manufacturing firms in Ibadan, Oyo State, Nigeria by utilize organizational justice theory The study shows that Industrial social workers should ensure that management of organization's give room for fair and just procedures (procedural justice and distributive justice) coupled with proper interaction (interactional justice) so that employees will be able to give better responses to the organization in terms of commitment, positive behavior and increased productivity.From the research it is ascertained that organizational justice led to strong organizational commitment (Ajala, 2015).

2.2 ORGANIZATIONAL JUSTICE AND PERCEIVED ORGANIZATIONAL SUPPORT

According to PoojaPurang the study has been highlighted the importance of perceived organizational support as the mechanism by which organizational justice impacts employee attitudes. Fair and favorable outcomes as well as procedures are perceived by the employees as a sign of organizational support to which the employees feel obligated to reciprocate with loyalty and commitment. This study has practical implications for managers in both Indian and international contexts. It concludes that the importance of justice perceptions and organizational support in enhancing feelings of loyalty and identification with the organization. Most employers want their employees to be dedicated to the organization, to identify with the organizational goals and to work towards fulfilling them. Organizations, by providing positive work experiences through fair rewards and recognition, communicate that they value the employee's contribution (Purang, 2011)

When employees perceive that they are receiving fair treatment in comparison to their coworkers, they perceive more supported by the organization. Fair organizational procedures and policies yield major contributions to POS because such procedures and policies are often viewed as strongly under the control of the organization and central to employees' long-term interests (Kurtessis et al., 2015).

According to Wayne, Shore, Bommer, and Tetrick (2002) The study has found distributive that and procedural justice relate significantly with perceived organizational support, with procedural justice having a stronger relationship.

2.3 PERCEIVED ORGANIZATIONAL SUPPORT AND EMPLOYEE'S COMMITMENT

organizational support delivers safety for the employees. This is important as this feeling causes them to consider that their organization stands behind them. As a result, high organizational support can lead to effectiveness and productivity for any organization (Eisenberger et al. 1997).

In some researches, it is shown that those with high organizational support perceptions develop strong psychological commitment state (Van Knippenberg and Sleebos 2006).

It is possible to say that to enhance employees contribute and develop commitment to their organization employee's need to feel that we are important for the organization. Therefore, the level of employee's perceived organizational support plays important role in creating organizational commitment of employee (Currie and drollery,2006; Tumwesigye,2010).

According to fundanayir the study that conduct on relationship between perceive organizational support and teacher's employee commitment on primary school in turkey found that teachers compliance commitment is affected by organization justice and supervisor support however the relationship between them is negative and very low. Ozdevecioglu (2003) conclude that increased in the perception of organizational support affected continuance commitment at a low level. However, (Currie & Dollery2006) found that perception of organizational support was not a significant predictor of continuance commitment.

2.4 CONCEPTUAL FRAMEWORK MODEL OF THE STUDY

Based on the above review of the literature, a conceptual framework has been developed (Figure 1) to portray the relationship between organizational justice (independent variable), organizational support (the mediator) and employee commitment (dependent variable).

Source: - Developed by the researcher.

Figure .1 Conceptual Framework Model

3. RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

3.1. RESEARCH APPROACH

Research has two basic approaches that are quantitative approach and qualitative approach. Quantitative approach includes the generation of data in quantitative form which can be subjected to rigorous quantitative analysis in a formal and rigid fashion Kothari (2004). For this study quantitative research approach is employed to investigate the relationship between the three dimensions of organizational justices namely distributive justice, procedural justice and interactional justice (independent variables), perceived organizational support (as a mediator variable), and the employee commitment (dependent variable) using a questionnaire. Quantitative technique helps to explore, present, describe and examine relationships and trends within data and as it also helps to collect results in numerical and standardized data (Saunders, Lewis & Thorhill, 2009).

3.2. RESEARCH DESIGN

The research design is the program that guides the researcher on the process of collecting, analyzing and interpreting observations. The research design that implements for the study is explanatory research design, which intends to show the cause-and-effect relationship existing between the independent variable which is Organizational Justice, dependent variable which is employee commitment and mediating variable which is perceived organizational support of the study.

3.3. POPULATION AND SAMPLING PROCEDURE

According to Sekeran (2006) sample defined as a portion of the population that represents the entire population. Even though, including all employee's ideas on the analysis would have been better for conclusion and generalization, economically and operationally, it is very difficult to contact all employees in research. Therefore, taking a representative sample of the population of the employees is feasible. The study used Probability sampling method to select the participants from the population particularly simple random sampling. In probability sampling, all people within the research population have a specifiable chance of being selected. These types of

sample are used if the researcher wishes to explain, predict or generalize to the whole research population (Saunders, Lewis & Thornhill, 2016).

In order to decide the participant of the study, the formula of Yamane (1967) will use to calculate sample size this formula is selected because of the formula can provide for finite population. the study population total number and list of employees are available.

Yamane (1967) formulate the following simplified formula to calculate sample sizes cited in Israel (2009). In order to determine the sample size for the study, three key factors such as confidence interval, confidence level, and the population size are considered.

$$n = \frac{N}{1 + N(e)^2}$$

Where n is the sample size, N is the population size, and e is the level of precision/ confidence interval.

The study considers a 95% confidence level and a 5% confidence interval. Using the above statistical formula, the sample size of the study is determined as follows:

$$n = \frac{407}{1 + 407(0.05)^2}$$

$$n = \underline{\underline{202}}$$

Therefore, the sample size for 407 targeted population of the study is 202 employees.

Select the participants from all branch of Gondar city revenue office proportionally based on sample size and select each individual by using list of employees working in the organization and assign sequential number to each employee and select sample randomly using random number table.

3.4 VARIABLES AND MEASURES

This study used commitment as the dependent variable, the three types of organizational justice namely distributive justice, procedural justice, interactional justice are independent variables and perceived organization support as a mediating variable.

For measuring the study variables, well recognized and broadly used scales were adopted from the previous studies.

Organizational Justice:

Organizational justice has three separate components: distributive justice, procedural justice, and interactional justice. Each of these three components was measured using the scale developed by Niehoff, & Moorman (1993). The scale has 20 items. The first five items represent distributive justice. The second six items represent procedural justice. The remaining nine items represent the interactional justice. Each participant asked to score each of the 20 items on a five-point Likert scale from 1 = strongly disagree to 5 = strongly agree. Summation of the scores of the items for each component provide the score for the component with a minimum of five and a maximum of 25 (for distributive justice), a minimum of six and a maximum of 30 (for procedural justice), and a minimum of nine and a maximum of 45 (for interactional justice).

Perceived organizational support

Perceived organizational support was measured using seven-item scale developed by Eisenberger et al 1997). Each participant asked to score the degree of their perceived organizational support by using a five-point Likert scale ranging from 1 = strongly disagree to 5 = strongly agree. Summation of the scores of the items provide the score with a minimum of 7 and a maximum of 35.

Employee's commitment

Employee's commitment was measured using 15 items scale developed by Mowday (1979) organizational commitment questionnaire (OCQ). Each participant asked to score the degree of their commitment by using a five-point Likert scale ranging from 1 = strongly disagree to 5 = strongly agree. Summation of the scores of the items provide the score with a minimum of 15 and

a maximum of 75. The OCQ has wide acceptance in organizational behavior research (Benkhoff, 1997 & Mowday, 1999).

3.8 VALIDITY AND RELIABILITY

The issue of validity was addressed through the review of literature and adapting instruments used in previous research works. Reliability tested using Cronbach's alpha values for the items in each construct. According to Sekaran & Bougie (2016) reliabilities less than 0.60 are considered to be poor, those in the 0.70 range, acceptable, and those over 0.80 good.

3.9 DATA ANALYSIS

The quantitative nature and the purpose of the study is aiming to examining the relationship between organizational justice (i.e., distributive justice, procedural justice and interactional justice) and Employee's commitment and the mediating role of Perceived organizational support, the application of statistical techniques is a necessary requirement. Hence, the study used to analyze Statistical Package for the Social Science version 25 (SPSS) to hypothesis testing and preliminary data analysis.

4. RESULTS and DISCUSSIONS

This section summarizes demographic characteristics of the respondents age, sex, level of education and year of experience. The purpose of the demographic analysis in this research is to describe the characteristics of the respondent such as the proportion of males and females, sex, education level, and year of experience. The result of the frequency analysis is presented in Table 4.1 here below.

Table 4.1 Frequency table of Demographic profile of the respondents

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
S e A g e	18-25	22	10.9	10.9	10.9
	26-35	93	46.0	46.0	56.9
	36-45	67	33.2	33.2	90.1
	above 45	20	9.9	9.9	100.0
S e	male	91	45.0	45.0	45.0

	female	111	55.0	55.0	100.0
Educational Qualification	below diploma	8	4.0	4.0	4.0
	Diploma	56	27.7	27.7	31.7
	first degree	115	56.9	56.9	88.6
	second degree	23	11.4	11.4	100.0
Year of experience	below 5	47	23.3	23.3	23.3
	6-10	89	44.1	44.1	67.3
	11-15	51	25.2	25.2	92.6
	above 15	15	7.4	7.4	100.0
Marital Status	single	80	39.6	39.6	39.6
	married	109	54.0	54.0	93.6
	divorced	13	6.4	6.4	100.0

Source: Researcher's survey data output (2023)

4.1 RELIABILITY TEST

According to Sekaran and Bougie (2016) reliability of a measure is an indication of the stability and consistency which the instrument measures the concept and helps to assess the goodness of a measure. In conducting the reliability test using SPSS version 25, the researcher calculated Cronbach's alpha values for the items in each construct as indicated table 4.2 here below. According to Sekaran and Bougie (2016) reliabilities less than 0.60 are considered to be poor, those in the 0.70 range, acceptable, and those over 0.80 good.

Table 4.2 Reliability Analysis

Reliability Statistics	
Cronbach's Alpha	N of Items
Distributive justice	.763
procedural justice	.764
interactional justice	.901
Perceived organizational support	.831
Employee commitment	.795

As indicated in table 4.1 the Cronbach's alpha coefficients of for interactional justice and Perceived organizational support is above 0.80 which shows a good reliability of the variables of measurement. Similarly, Cronbach's alpha coefficient of distributive justice, procedural justice and employee commitment are also above 0.70 which indicates an acceptable reliability of the variables of measurement. The overall reliability of the measures used in this study can be considered to be acceptable.

4.3 REGRESSION ANALYSIS AND HYPOTHESIS TESTING

Each hypothesis proposed empirically tested and discussed in this part. Regression analyses were used to explore the relationship between the independent and dependent variables while for testing mediation the Baron and Kenny (1986) model used as a guiding framework. The coefficients of determination (R square value), the regression coefficients (Beta coefficient) and the p-values for each of the significant relationships were reported.

4.3.1 Regression Model Specification

Model 1

H1: Distributive justice affects employee commitment positively.

H2: Procedural justice affects employee commitment positively

H3: Interactional justice affect employee commitment positively

$$\text{Com} = \beta_0 + a_1\text{DJ} + a_2\text{PJ} + a_3\text{IJ} + e \quad \text{..... model 1}$$

Where: com= Employee commitment, DJ = Distributive Justice, PJ = Procedural Justice, IJ = Interactional Justice, β_0 = intercept of employee commitment, a_1 , a_2 , a_3 = coefficients, e = the random error

Model 2

H5: Distributive justice affect perceived organizational support positively

H6: Procedural justice affect perceived organizational support positively

H7: Interactional justice affect perceived organizational support positively

$$\text{pos} = \beta_1 + b_1\text{DJ} + b_2\text{PJ} + b_3\text{IJ} + e \quad \text{..... model 2}$$

Where: pos= perceived organizational support, DJ = Distributive Justice, PJ = Procedural Justice, IJ = Interactional Justice, β_1 = intercept of perceived organizational support, b_1, b_2, b_3 = coefficients, e = the random error

Model 3

H8: perceived organizational support mediates the relationship between distributive justice and employee commitment

H9: perceived organizational support mediates the relationship between procedural justice and employee commitment

H10: perceived organizational support mediates the relationship between interactional justice and employee commitment.

$$Com = \beta_2 + c_1DJ + c_2PJ + c_3IJ + c_4POS + e \dots\dots\dots \text{model 3}$$

Where: com= Employeecommitment, DJ = Distributive Justice, PJ = Procedural Justice, IJ = Interactional Justice, POS= perceived organizational support, β_2 = intercept of employeecommitment, c_1, c_2, c_3, c_4 = coefficients, e = the random error

Model 4

H4: perceived organizational support affect employee commitment positively

$$Com = \beta_3 + d_1POS + e \dots\dots\dots \text{model 4}$$

Where: com= Employeecommitment, POS= perceived organizational support, β_3 = intercept of employeecommitment, d_1 = coefficients, e = the random error

4.5.2 Regression analysis

Table 4.6 Model Summary

Model Summary									
Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate	Change Statistics				Sig. F Change
					R Square Change	F Change	df1	df2	

1	.285 ^a	.081	.067	.64842	.081	5.818	3	198	.001
a. Predictors: (Constant), Distributive Justice, Interactional Justice, Procedural Justice									
2	.609 ^a	.371	.361	.72515	.371	38.928	3	198	.000
a. Predictors: (Constant), Distributive Justice, Interactional Justice, Procedural Justice									
3	.558 ^a	.312	.298	.56252	.312	22.370	4	197	.000
a. Predictors: (Constant), Distributive Justice, Interactional Justice, Procedural Justice, Organizational support									
4	.549 ^a	.301	.298	.56254	.301	86.258	1	200	.000

a. Predictors: (Constant), Organizational support

Source: Researcher's survey data output (2021)

As clearly described in table 4.6 here above R-square value for the regression Model 1 was 0.081. This indicates that organizational justice (i.e., distributive justice, procedural justice and interactional justice) in this study explain about 8.1% of the variation in the level of employee commitment. Similarly, the R-square value for the regression model 2 was 0.371. This indicates that organizational justice (i.e., distributive justice, procedural justice and interactional justice) in this study explain about 37.1% of the variation in the level of perceived organization support.

From the regression model 3 Presented in table 4.6, a value of R=0.312, indicates a positive prediction of the independent variable's (organizational justice(i.e., distributive justice, procedural justice and interactional justice) and perceived organization support) on the dependent variable (employee commitment). The R square value of 0.312 indicated that, the proportion of variance in the effect that can be accounted for by the predictors. Thus, the result implied that 31.2% of the variation in employees' organizational commitment jointly explained by the predictors, i.e., organization justice and perceived organizational support.

The model summary indicated that perceived organization support explained 30.1% of the variation in employee commitment in model 4.

Table 4.4 ANOVA

Model		Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	7.339	3	2.446	5.818	.001 ^b
	Residual	83.249	198	.420		
	Total	90.587	201			

a. Dependent Variable: Employee commitment

b. Predictors: (Constant), Distributive Justice, Interactional Justice, Procedural Justice

2	Regression	61.408	3	20.469	38.928	.000 ^b
	Residual	104.116	198	.526		
	Total	165.524	201			

a. Dependent Variable: Organizational support

b. Predictors: (Constant), Distributive Justice, Interactional Justice, Procedural Justice

3	Regression	28.251	4	7.063	22.320	.000 ^b
	Residual	62.337	197	.316		
	Total	90.587	201			

a. Dependent Variable: Employee commitment

b. Predictors: (Constant), Organizational support, Distributive Justice, Interactional Justice, Procedural Justice

4	Regression	27.297	1	27.297	86.258	.000 ^b
	Residual	63.291	200	.316		
	Total	90.587	201			

a. Dependent Variable: Employee commitment

b. Predictors: (Constant), Organizational support

Source: Researcher's survey data output (2021)

As indicated in the ANOVA table (table 4.7) here above the p – value (0.000 and 0.001) is less than 0.05 significant level. This implies that the sample data provides sufficient evidence to conclude that the regression model was well fit. In other words, the p – value (0.000) is highly significant and can be concluded that organizational justice (i.e., distributive justice, procedural justice and interactional justice) can predict employee commitment and perceived organizational support significantly. Therefore, based on a given results the multiple linear regression model is appropriate to this research to predict the effects of organizational justice and perceived organizational support with employee commitment

4.5.3 Testing the Research Hypothesis

As it is stated in the objectives of this study the main aims to identify the effect level of independent variables (organizational justice) in the prediction of the dependent variable (employee commitment). Thus, the strength of each predictor (independent) variable influence on the criterion (dependent) variable can be investigated via unstandardized Beta coefficient. Hence, the regression coefficients explain the average amount of change in employee commitment (dependent variable) that caused by a unit of change in the organizational justice components (independent variable). In order to determine which of the factors contributed to prediction of employee commitment, the unstandardized regression coefficients or beta weights (β) were examined in below Table 4.8.

Table 4.8 Coefficient (Model 1)

Coefficients^a						
Model	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.	
	B	Std. Error	Beta			
1	(Constant)	2.454	.179		13.725	.000
	Distributive Justice	.184	.052	.245	3.578	.000
	Procedural Justice	.192	.053	.247	3.597	.000
	Interactional Justice	.179	.048	.253	3.695	.000

a. Dependent Variable: Employee commitment

Source: Researcher's survey data output (2021)

In order to achieve the objectives of this study the following hypothesis of the study were tested as stated in chapter one and two and the result of the analysis presented below. The tests are done based on the unstandardized coefficient of beta and p-value based on table 4.8

H1: Distributive justice affects employee commitment positively in Gondar city administration revenue office.

As a result, indicate in table 4.8, there is a significant ($\beta = 0.184$, $p=.000$) positive relationship between distributive justice and employee commitment in Gondar city administration revenue

office. Based on these finding, hypotheses one there is statistically significant relationship between distributive justice and employee commitment to be accepted. The study concluded that there is statistically significant relationship between distributive justice and employee commitment in Gondar city administration revenue office.

H2: Procedural justice affects employee commitment positively in Gondar city administration revenue office.

As a result, indicate in table 4.8, there is a significant ($\beta = 0.192$, $p=.000$) positive relationship between Procedural justice and employee commitment in Gondar city administration revenue office. Based on these finding, hypotheses one there is statistically significant relationship between Procedural justice and employee commitment to be accepted. The study concluded that there is statistically significant relationship between Procedural justice and employee commitment in Gondar city administration revenue office.

H3: Interactional justice affect employee commitment positively in Gondar city administration revenue office.

The result shows there is a positive and significant relationship between Interactional justice and employee's commitment, ($\beta = 0.179$, $p=.000$) in Gondar city administration revenue office. Based on these finding, hypotheses two there is statistically significant relationship between Interactional justice and employee commitment to be accepted. Hence, the researcher concluded that there is statistically significant relationship between Interactional justice and employee commitment in Gondar city administration revenue office.

Table 4.9 Coefficient (Model 2)

		Coefficients ^a				
		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	T	Sig.
Model		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	1.076	.200		5.379	.000
	Distributive Justice	.258	.080	.254	3.241	.001
	Procedural Justice	.466	.067	.444	7.000	.000
	Interactional Justice	.437	.076	.456	5.760	.000

a. Dependent Variable: Organizational support

Source: Researcher's survey data output (2021)

H5: Distributive justice affect perceived organizational support positively

The regression coefficient result of model 2 shows that (see table 4.9) there was a significant positive relationship between distributive justice and perceived organizational support in Gondar city administration revenue office ($\beta = 0.258$, $p = 0.001$). Thus, the study result supports the hypothesis (H5). The study concluded that there is statistically significant relationship between Distributive justice and perceived organizational support in Gondar city administration revenue office.

H6: Procedural justice affect perceived organizational support positively

The regression coefficient result of model 2 shows that (see table 4.9) there was a significant positive relationship between Procedural justice and perceived organizational support in Gondar city administration revenue office ($\beta = 0.466$, $p = 0.000$). Thus, the study result supports the hypothesis (H6). The study concluded that there is statistically significant relationship between Procedural justice and perceived organizational support in Gondar city administration revenue office.

H7: Interactional justice affect perceived organizational support positively

The regression coefficient result of model 2 shows that (see table 4.9) there was a significant positive relationship between: Interactional justice and perceived organizational support in Gondar city administration revenue office ($\beta = 0.437$, $p = 0.000$). Thus, the study result supports the hypothesis (H7). The study concluded that there is statistically significant relationship between : Interactional justice and perceived organizational support in Gondar city administration revenue office.

Table 4.10 Coefficient (Model 4)

Coefficients^a

Model	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
	B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	1.958	.136	14.415	.000
	Organizational support	.406	.044	.549	.000

a. Dependent Variable: Employee commitment

Source: Researcher's survey data output (2021)

H4: perceived organizational support affect employee commitment positively

Based on the regression result beta value of ($\beta = 0.406$, $p = .000$). This means that, perceived organizational support had positive influence on employees' organizational commitment. The result revealed that, when perceived organizational support increase by 1% level of employee commitment also increased by 40.6%. This implies perceived organizational support has positive and significant influence for enhancing level of employee commitment. Thus, the above hypothesis (H4) is accepted.

In summary, results indicated that distributive justice, procedural justice, interactional justice has significant and positive effect with employee commitment. The three dimensions of organizational justice also have positive and significant effect with perceived organizational support. Furthermore, the result showed that perceived organizational support also has positive and significant effect with employee turnover intention. Therefore, the results reported in table 4.8, 4.9 and 4.10 supports hypotheses H1, H2, H3, H4, H5, H6 and H7.

4.5.4 Mediation Testing with Regression Analysis

In order to undertake mediation test Baron and Kenny's (1986) model for testing mediation was used as a guiding framework. Accordingly, mediation was tested through three regression models (Baron and Kenny, 1986; Field, 2013; Hayes, 2013). According to Field (2013) the three regression models are (I) A regression model that predicts the dependent variable from the independent dependent variable, (II) A regression model that predicts the mediator variable from independent variable, and (III) A regression model that predicts dependent variable from both the independent variable and mediator variable. Furthermore, in Baron and Kenny's (1986)

mediation testing model four conditions must be met for a variable to be considered as a mediator. These are (i) the independent variable must be significantly related to the dependent variable in model 1; (ii) the independent variable must be significantly related to the mediator in model 2; (iii) the mediator must be significantly related to the dependent variable in model 3; and finally (iv) the independent variable must predict the dependent variable either become insignificant (total mediation) or become less significant (partial mediation) in model 3 than in model 1 (Baron and Kenny, 1986; Field, 2013; Shuck et al., 2014).

The regression results of model 1 (see table 4.8) showed that the three dimensions of organizational justice (i.e., distributive justice, procedural justice and interactional justice) are positively related with employee commitment ($\beta_1 = 0.184$, $\beta_2 = 0.192$, $\beta_3 = 0.179$, $p = 0.000$). Thus, the first condition is fulfilled.

The regression analysis result indicated in table 4.9 shows that there is significant positive relationship between the three dimensions of organizational justice (i.e., distributive justice, procedural justice and interactional justice) and perceived organizational support (the mediator variable) ($\beta_1 = 0.258$, $\beta_2 = 0.466$, $\beta_3 = 0.437$, $p = 0.000$). Therefore, the second condition is satisfied.

Table 4.11 Coefficient (Model 3)

		Coefficients ^a				
		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients		
Model		B	Std. Error	Beta	t	Sig.
1	(Constant)	1.972	.166		11.875	.000
	Distributive Justice	-.029	.063	-.038	-.456	.649
	Procedural Justice	.080	.071	.103	1.119	.264
	Interactional Justice	-.102	.064	-.145	-1.610	.109
	Organizational support	.448	.055	.606	8.129	.000

a. Dependent Variable: Employee commitment

The regression analysis result of model 3 as indicated in table 4.11 here above shows that even though the regression coefficient for the mediator variable (perceived organizational support) is positively related with the dependent variable (employee commitment), it is statistically

significant. This implies that the third condition is fulfilled. The fourth condition states the independent variable must predict the dependent variable either become insignificant (total mediation) or become less significant (partial mediation) in model 3 than in model 1, Therefore,

H8: perceived organizational support mediates the relationship between distributive justice and employee commitment

the regression coefficients show that the main effect of distributive justice on employee commitment becomes insignificant when mediating variable (perceived organizational support) is introduced to the equation ($p = .649$) p value > 0.05 . Thus, hypothesis (**H8**) is accepted

H9: perceived organizational support mediates the relationship between procedural justice and employee commitment

the regression coefficients show that the effect of procedural justice on employee commitment is insignificant when mediating variable (perceived organizational support) is introduced to the equation ($p = .264$) p value > 0.05 . Thus, hypothesis (**H9**) is accepted

H10: perceived organizational support mediates the relationship between interactional justice and employee commitment.

the regression coefficients show that the effect of interactional justice on employee commitment also becomes insignificant when mediating variable (perceived organizational support) is introduced to the equation ($p = .109$) p value > 0.05 . Thus, hypothesis (**H10**) is accepted. This implies that the indirect relationship exists between organizational justice (i.e., distributive justice, procedural justice and interactional justice) and employee commitment through perceived organizational support.

In summary it can be concluded that perceived organizational support fully mediates the relationship between organizational justice (i.e., distributive justice, procedural justice, interactional justice) and employee commitment.

CONCLUSIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS

The objective of this study was to examine the mediating role of perceived organizational support in the relationship between organizational justices (i.e., distributive justice, procedural justice and interactional justice) and employee commitment in the context of Gondar city administration revenue office.

Based on the objective of the study and hypotheses, the questionnaire (survey instruments) for measuring the research variables were selected and organized. As a result, the organizational justice was measured using five, six and nine item scale for distributive justice, procedural justice and interactional justice respectively measurement scale developed by Niehoff and Moorman (1993), perceived organizational support was measured using the seven-item POS measurement scale developed by Eisenberger et al 1997) and employee commitment was measured using the fifteen items OCQ scale developed by Mowday (1997). Of 202 distributed questionnaires 202 (100%) questionnaires were collected and used for analysis. The collected data was analyzed using statistical package for social science software (SPSS). Regression analyses were employed for testing the hypotheses.

Prior to applying regression analysis for testing the research hypothesis, reliability, correlation analysis and other preliminary tests (like multicollinearity, linearity, normality test) were performed. With regard to the reliability, the results showed that all measures used in this study had an acceptable level of reliability above 0.70. Pearson correlation also indicated no problem with multicollinearity. With regard to other preliminary testes the results showed that there were no significant data problems that would lead to say the assumptions of regression analysis had been seriously violated.

The overall results of hypotheses testing indicated that distributive justice, procedural justice, and interactional justice have significant and positive effect with employee commitment ($\beta = 0.184, p=.000$), ($\beta = 0.192, p=.000$), ($\beta = 0.179, p=.000$) respectively. Similarly, the results also confirmed that the three dimensions of organizational justice (i.e., distributive justice, procedural justice and interactional justice) have positive and significant effect with perceived organizational support ($\beta = 0.258, p=.001$), ($\beta = 0.466, p=.000$), ($\beta = 0.437, p=.000$) respectively. perceived organizational support also has positive and significant effect with employee commitment ($\beta = 0.406, p=.000$). With regard to the mediating role of perceived organizational support had fully mediating role in the relationship between organizational justice (i.e.,

distributive justice, procedural justice and interactional justice) and employee commitment the results showed that perceived organizational support had mediating role on the relationship between distributive justice and employee commitment, procedural justice and employee commitment. and interactional justice and employee commitment. Therefore, the results reported in this study supports all hypotheses H1, H2, H3, H4, H5, H6, H7, H8, H9 and H10.

5.1 CONCLUSION

This study was initiated to examine the effect of organizational justice on employee commitment and examine perceived organizational support as a mediating role in Gondar city administration revenue office.

The results of the study established strong support for the positive relationship between organizational justice and employee commitment. Specifically, the results showed that the three dimensions of organizational justice namely distributive justice, procedural justice, and interactional justice were positive related to employee commitment. Such a relationship implies that when employees perceive that they have been treated fairly, the higher the employee commitment to stay the organization. The results of the study also showed that among the three dimensions of organizational justice procedural justice predicts employee commitment in the Gondar city administration revenue office more than the other dimensions of organizational justice followed by distributive justice. This implies that fairness and transparency of the processes how decisions are made in terms of rewards, promotions, resource allocation, etc. are critical aspects that influence the employees of Gondar city administration revenue office.

The results of the study confirmed that organizational justice (i.e., distributive justice, procedural justice and interactional justice) has positive relationship. A positive significant relationship was found between distributive justice, procedural justice and interactional justice with perceived organizational support. Studies have found that organizational rewards, interpersonal relation and favorable job conditions (such as good pay, promotions, job enrichment and transparency of the processes) contribute to the perceived organizational support. As a result, when employees have high perceptions of justice in their work place, they are more likely obliged to be fair in performing their roles. On the other hand, low perceptions of fairness are likely to cause employees to disengage themselves from their work roles. The results of the study also showed

that among the three dimensions of organizational justice, interactional justice, procedural justice and distributive justice was the better contributor of perceived organizational support in Gondar city revenue office respectively. This implies that, interpersonal treatment, communication, fairness, transparency of the processes how decisions are made and organization reward are important aspects to contribute organizational support.

The result of the study indicated that perceived organizational support has positive and significant relationship with employee commitment. As a result, the higher-level perceived organizational support results in higher levels of employee commitment.

The result of the study confirmed that perceived organizational support has a mediating role on the relationship between Organizational justice and employee commitment. This implies that the indirect relationship exists between organizational justice (i.e., distributive justice, procedural justice and interactional justice) and employee commitment through perceived organization support.

5.2 RECOMMENDATION

Based on the findings and the conclusions the following recommendations were forwarded:

Employees have high perception of fairness in their work place they are highly committed to work on the other hand employee have low perception of justice or fairness are likely to cause employees have low level of commitment to their work. The management of the Gondar city revenue office should enhance perception of fairness through promoting the dimension (i.e., distributive justice, procedural justice and interactional justice) those variables are a good predictor of organizational commitment.

To enhance distributive justice the management of the Gondar city revenue office should be have rules and regulation used to distribute benefits, rewards and they should enable to employee feel satisfaction with their work outcome.

To promote the procedural justice the management of the Gondar city revenue office should concern about fairness of procedural component, transparency of process how decisions are

made and create favorable work condition in order to create positive perception of justice that helps to increase employee commitment.

To increase interactional justice the management of the Gondar city revenue office should develop a culture of truthfulness, understanding of workers interest, caring, interpersonal treatment, kindness with their subordinates, good communication and provide right information it helps to improve the perception of justice.

Perceived organizational support also a good predictors of employee commitment the management of the Gondar city revenue office should help employees in a situation of need (illness), give fair money compensation, career development, work recognition, company loan and inspire them through satisfactory working environment.

Organizational reward, interpersonal relationship, favorable working environment, good communication, friendliness, fairness of procedure component those are contributed to employees who perceive the organization support it leads to employee have committed and performing their role very well.

REFERENCE

- Aboagye, E. S. (2015). *A study of the dimensions of organizational justice which best predict employee trust and productivity in Ghanaian higher education institutions* (Doctoral dissertation, University of Ghana).
- Adams, J. S. (1965). Inequity in social exchange. In *Advances in experimental social psychology* (Vol. 2, pp. 267-299). Academic Press.
- Ajala, E. M. (2015). The influence of organizational justice on employees' commitment in manufacturing firms in Oyo State, Nigeria: implications for industrial social work. *African Journal of Social Work*, 5(1), 92-130.
- Akanbi, Ayobami, P., Ofoegbu, & Eugene, O. (2013). Impact of perceived organizational justice on organizational commitment of a food and beverage firm in Nigeria. *International Journal of Humanities and Social Sciences*. vol.3(14)., 207-218
- Akram, T., Haider, M. J., & Feng, Y. X. (2016). The effects of organizational justice on the innovative work behavior of employees: an empirical study from China. *Innovation*, 2(1), 114-126.

- Ali, I., Rehman, K. U., Ali, S. I., Yousaf, J., & Zia, M. (2010). Corporate social responsibility influences, employee commitment and organizational performance. *African journal of Business management*, 4(13), 2796-2801.
- Allen, N. J., & Meyer, J. P. (1996). Affective, continuance, and normative commitment to the organization: An examination of construct validity. *Journal of vocational behavior*, 49(3), 252-276.
- Greenberg, J., & Cropanzano, R. (1993). The social side of fairness: Interpersonal and informational classes of organizational justice. *Justice in the workplace: Approaching fairness in human resource management*. Hillsdale, NJ: Lawrence Erlbaum Associates.
- Gürbüz, S., & Mert, I. S. (2009). Validity and reliability testing of organizational justice scale: An empirical study in a public organization. *Review of Public Administration*, 42(3), 117-139.
- Hassan, A. (2002). Organizational justice as a determinant of organizational commitment and intention to leave. *Asian Academy of Management Journal*, 7(2), 55-66.
- He, H., Zhu, W., & Zheng, X. (2014). Procedural justice and employee engagement: Roles of organizational identification and moral identity centrality. *Journal of business ethics*, 122(4), 681-695.
- Israel Glenn D. (2009), Determining Sample Size; It is a PEOD6 document, one of a series of the Agricultural Education and Communication Department, Florida Cooperative Extension Service, Institute of Food and Agricultural Sciences, University of Florida. Original publication date November 1992. Revised April 2009. Reviewed June 2012.
- Iverson, R. D., & Buttigieg, D. M. (1999). Affective, normative and continuance commitment: can the 'right kind' of commitment be managed? *Journal of management studies*, 36(3), 307-333.
- Jaros, S. (2007). Meyer and Allen model of organizational commitment: Measurement issues. *The Icfai Journal of Organizational Behavior*, 6(4), 7-25.
- Kofi, H., Asiamah, N. and Mireku, K. (2016), "The effect of organizational justice delivery on organizational commitment: controlling for key confounding variables", *Journal of Global Responsibility*, Vol. 7 No. 2, pp. 1-14.
- Kothari, C. R. (2004). *Research methodology: Methods and techniques*. New Age International.

- Krishnan, J., & Mary, V. S. (2012). Perceived organisational support—an overview on its antecedents and consequences. *International Journal of Multidisciplinary Research*, 2(4), 2-3.
- Kurtessis, J., Eisenberger, R., Ford, M. T., Buffardi, L. C., Stewart, K. A., & Adis, C. A. (2015). Perceived organizational support: a meta-analytic.
- Lather, A. S., & KAUR, M. (2015). Evolution of the Concept of Organizational Justice'. *Asia Pacific Journal of Research*, 1(29), 7-25.
- Tumwesigye, G. (2010). The relationship between perceived organisational support and turnover intentions in a developing country: The mediating role of organisational commitment. *African Journal of Business Management*, 4(6), 942-952.
- Van Knippenberg D, Sleebos E 2006. Organizational identification versus organizational commitment: self-definition, social exchange, and job attitudes. *Journal of Organizational Behavior*, 27(5): 571–584.
- Wei, G. U. O., & Tai, L. I. (2010, May). An empirical study on organizational commitment and turnover of it industry. In *2010 International Conference on E-Business and E-Government* (pp. 904-906). IEEE.
- Yamane, T. (1967). *Statistics: An Introductory Analysis*. (2nd edn). New York: Harper and Row.
- Yean, T. F. (2016). Organizational justice: A conceptual discussion. *Procedia-Social and Behavioral Sciences*, 219, 798-803.
- Zeyede, h. G. (2019). *The effect of organizational justice on employees 'job satisfaction in commercial bank of ethiopia in case of debrebrhan town* (doctoral dissertation).
- zikmund, g. w. (2010). *business research methods: a practical guide*. new york:: south-western/thomson publication.